

ASPECTS OF ISRAEL'S DEMOCRATIZATION THROUGH THE STRENGTHENING OF THE STATEHOOD

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The article analyzes the multilateral political aspects of Israel evolution from the creation of the state to the present, especially referred to the electoral reform development. The study demonstrates that the creation of political coalitions is an imperfect structural problem in Israel requiring a solution; the failure of the early reforms, to solve the problem in question, indicates that the peaceful solution is impossible in Israel.

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Israel is unique in the world with its system of proportional representation and the perpetual need for coalition formation. Israel presents an interesting example of the functions of democracy with its many divisions - religious, ethnic and ideological. The complexity of these issues is vital to studying the functioning of democracy. The case of Israel cannot be taken apart as something isolated but must be regarded as an extreme and very complicated case. In 1992, Israel experienced a reform of the political and deep electoral system that was implemented in 1996. This reform has several elements. The most significant is that now the Israelis vote directly on the prime minister. The new system combines elements of both presidential and parliamentary systems, despite the fact that they are very different and their merger can cause great problems. The intention of the reform - to extend the

prerogatives of the executive branch - has not been transposed into life. It's interesting to understand why.

There is a link between electoral rules, political institutions and the decision-making process. Any change in the configuration of decisions or rules can have a decisive influence on collective outcomes. Just before the end of the fighting in the war of independence, the Israelis were urged to vote for their political representatives. Elections took place in November 1949, more than 415,000 voters supported 21 competing parties. Only 12 of them have passed the 1% electoral threshold and have obtained mandates for the Knesset. But these choices and choices for I Knesset were actually meant for something else. The people came to vote for their representatives in the Constitutional Assembly, it was supposed to be a body of 120 members who would formulate and

adopt a democratic constitution. Once, however, after several debates among members of the secular and religious factions, it was decided that Israel already had a very good constitution – the Bible and the adoption of the Constitution was postponed and the Assembly transformed into Parliament. The Knesset once formed in the 1950s had to adopt a few laws. Some of the fundamental laws were promulgated by the Knesset in its capacity. These laws are called Fundamental Laws. Fifty years later, however, Israel does not have a written Constitution. Political life and other aspects of social life are guided by these fundamental laws, laws, regulations and ordinances. However, ten fundamental laws have not yet been adopted. They include laws that include the following spheres: Knesset, government, president, army, economy, land of Israel, individual freedom and dignity and freedom of occupation. The first six Basic Laws define the institutional and political arrangements of the state [1].

The Jerusalem Law is of significance and symbolic value and states that this city is „unified and complete and is the capital of Israel“. The Israeli land law declares that only 5% of these lands are private and all of them are leased by Israeli citizens for a certain period of time. The last two laws were adopted in 1992 and are essentially liberal, they focus more on individual rights. Important and varied decisions were taken along the opening of the Assemble and during its operation.

So far, it is still unclear what the international boundaries of Israel are. The issue remains as long as there is a conflict between Israel and the Arabs, particularly with the Palestinians. Only in 1979 the southern boundaries between Israel and Egypt were defined, and in 1994 only the eastern ones with Jordan, and in 1999 the northern boundaries with Lebanon for the northeast (Syria) and those with Palestine are not yet determined. The non-liberal nature of democracy in Israel is well illustrated by addressing the issue of citizenship. Because the state belongs to the Jewish people who is an unclear ethnicity, it does not belong to its citizens. This means that Jews outside the country actually have more rights than the non-Jewish Arab citizens of Israel (who were more than 5% of the population by 1999). The Return Law, which was adopted by Knesset in 1950, provides and gives citizenship to any of the Jews who return to the country. The emigration of the diaspora Jews in Israel is the main credo of the Zionist movement - a movement that promotes Jewish nationalism.

When a fragmented society has an electoral system that encourages more parties, it is also obvious the difficult formation of the majority of the government. Such is Israel's case. Israel's electoral reform has not only failed to attack this fundamental problem, but it has made it even worse.

Israel's political system is originally intended to represent the interests of different voters, but this is problematic because of the disproportionality that is given to minorities. In order to alleviate these

difficulties, reforms were initiated for the 1996 elections. By the direct election of the prime minister, the reformers hoped to amplify the prime minister's office and thereby diminish the disproportionality of the influence of small parties. So they hoped to increase the prime minister's ability to govern and thus contribute to the stability of Israel's democracy. However, the election results of 1996 and 1999 have not yet met these expectations. Israel's electoral reforms have come out because reformers have not considered a crucial moment for the process in question. Reforms have been made to give the Prime Minister the minimum need to depend on small parties to strengthen his power. Under the new system, voters were faced with not only voting for an individual prime minister, but also choosing a different party for the Knesset. Voters began voting more for small parties, continuing to limit the prime minister's ability to govern. Prior to the 1996 elections, the President was the one who called the leader of the largest party to form the government. This is why voters were encouraged to vote for the party whose leader they wanted to be prime minister. The new system allowed them to vote directly for both the prime minister and a different party who thought they would represent their specific interests and needs. It should be noted that after the electoral reform there was no evidence that the governments of Israel were stronger than they were before. Political and electoral systems, as well as the rules they create, provide the government's operating framework and thus offer it the

legitimacy to process. Moreover, they provide the main link between mandates and votes.

Israel's political system has a high level of inclusion, it offers many people and groups to be represented and to compete for resources. With so many small parties represented in the Knesset, the reform of the electoral system becomes very difficult. Prior to the current electoral reform, the Israeli system was a parliamentary democracy with a single voting district of 120 members elected every four years. Each party will have its candidate list, create the platform, and seek support from the electorate. All parties that have obtained the minimum required votes will receive a proportion of seats equal to their total proportion of votes. Mandates were granted according to the Largest Remainder Formula system (used in Israel from 1951 to 1973) or Highest Average (D'hondt) System, which was used in 1949 and then since 1973 to the present [2].

This system is known in Israel as the Bader-Ofer system, after two politicians who introduced it. This application of only one district combined with a small threshold for obtaining mandates causes the public and individuals to think that it is easier to get at least one place in the Knesset. Moreover, no party has ever obtained a majority of votes. It is therefore clear that all governments had to be coalitions, in fact the very majority of the Israeli policies are coalition constructions. To understand the political system in Israel, attention must be drawn to the process and rules of coalition formation that begin as

soon as the elections are over. The president consults the leaders of each party and determines who should entrust the formation of the government. The leader of the elected party is given 21 days to form a government and present the list of the Knesset.

If he is incapable of forming his government, he is given another 21 days or another leader is appointed to monitor the achievement of the given goal. When the new government is approved by the Knesset, the coalition formation process is finished. During the old system, the government could not have been approved by the Knesset for 4-5 years, and even during that time it could receive the vote of non-confidentiality. Gideon Doron mentions that the 1948-1992 political system in Israel was based on the governance structure that served Yishuv (the Jewish Community of Palestine before independence) [3].

The roots of this trend come from the 19th century, the early period of the Zionist movement. In order to have supporters and to form a strong image on the international arena, the Zionist Movement had to recruit as many followers. One way to achieve this goal was to adopt a relatively generous system of representation that allows the inclusion of several groups from the small to the large groups of Jewish communities spread throughout Europe and the world. There has never been a systematic debate on what political system should be. Since the Independence War began on the first day after the nation declared statehood, there was only the so-called academic time for debates

on the best governance system. We should also take into account that a powerful influence was exercised by the British system on the Israel system implemented in 1948. Israel now called Palestine was governed by the British authorities between 1917 and 1948 [4].

Through strong cooperation and struggle, the Jewish people began to study to understand and adopt a system similar to the British governing system. The British system was well suited to the socialist tendencies of many early Zionists. However, a difficulty arose with this arrangement that Israel is not Britain. Bagehot argues that „the characteristics of the British Constitution are inapplicable in countries where there is no material for monarchy or aristocracy” [5]. So there was a need for a system that fits perfectly with the unique circumstances of Israel, so it is no wonder that this system has proved imperfect. The proposal to elect the direct prime minister was adopted as a law (Fundamental Law of the Government) in 1992 in the last days of the 12th Knesset. This idea was discussed between March and June 1990. Then Likud and the Labor Party struggled to form minimal leadership coalitions to dissolve the second National Government. They came up with initiatives to make changes in the Prime Minister's election. This had to diminish the dependence of the Prime Minister of Knesset. Prime Minister Shamir and many Likud party representatives opposed this proposal, being concerned that Ytzhak Rabin could be elected in direct elections.

However, after the consolidated debates on the last day of the 12th Knesset, the reform passed and maintained not only the Prime Minister's direct election idea, but also the proposal that the non-confidentiality vote would mean the resignation of the Knesset. The reforms undertaken in 1992 were aimed at enhancing the legitimacy and power of the Prime Minister. And, it was not intended to limit the power of small parties at all what was actually believed to be. If we look at the 1996 election results, we will notice the dramatic shift of power from the big parties (Labourist and Likud) to the smallest. The two parties that won in 1992, 84 Knesset manuscripts in the 1996 elections, managed to receive only 66 and only 45 in 1999. In 1996, other parties such as Shas, the National Party and Hadash have considerably increased their Knesset mandate to 67, 50 and 67 percent, and this trend followed in the 1999 elections when Shas increased the percentage up to 70. However, the new system implemented in 1996 has resulted not only in the transfer of power from large to small already existing parties, but has also made many new parties obtain representation in the Knesset. The record of 35 parties that participated in the 1999 elections and 15 who obtained mandates in the Knesset demonstrates that they have passed the electoral threshold of 1.5% [6].

Although Netanyahu in 1996 and Barak in 1999 were directly elected as prime ministers, they had to form coalitions as party leaders who had only 32 seats in Netanyahu's case and 36 in Barak's case. This

was caused by the small threshold that allowed many small parties to be represented in the Knesset, and thus the prime minister elected was faced with forming coalitions of government. The reform was aimed at widening Prime Minister's prerogatives and minimizing his dependence on the Knesset, but this was not achieved. In the 1996 and 1999 elections, Israeli voters proved to be more sophisticated than the reformers expected. The size of the two large parties dropped to 55 percent in Knesset (1996) and 37 percent in 1999 [6].

However, attempts have been made to change the political system and improve electoral reform, ie to exclude direct elections. Uzi Landau (Likud) and Yossi Beilin (Labor), who cooperated for the new reform, proposed a piece of legislation, while Moshe Shahal of the Labourists proposed another. Landau-Beilin proposed that Israel either return to the old system or Prime Minister will be elected by the Knesset, each party presenting its candidate for the vote. Beilin argued that the new law weakened large parties, and Shahal noticed that small parties grew much in the leverage. However, politicians are concerned that reforms, on the one hand, lead to problem solving and, on the other hand, create new problems [7]. This proposal is supported by several members of the Likud party. The process of forming coalitions is inherently linked to the government's ability to make decisions and rule. Coalition issues were part of the political reality of Israel in 1948 and intensified in the late 1970s.

The implementation of the 1992 electoral reform demonstrates that the creation of coalitions is an imperfect structural problem requiring a solution; the failure of the early reforms, to solve the problem in question, indicates that the peaceful solution is impossible in Israel. The inability of the political system in Israel to

resolve or at least address seriously this issue over several decades may be a sign that the problem is impossible to solve in this state. However, acknowledging that the issue has serious implications for the government, political process and democratic founding of the state can make Knesset deputies look for a more effective reform in the field.

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